

Determination of Variation in Dimensions of Lumbar Vertebral Pedicles among Indian Adult Population

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Abstract

Introduction: An operating surgeon can carry out these treatments more accurately and safely if they are aware of slight anatomical heterogeneity. Prior to implant implantation, general orthopedic surgery guidelines encourage templating with precise measurements. It is known that there is a significant discrepancy between both the historically recorded diameter of the outer cortical and the effective cancellous diameter, suggesting that a safe screw selection might not always be possible with the use of traditional methods. It is strongly believed by the surgeon community that appropriate morphometric information on the lumbar pedicles is essential to undertake these treatments in a risk-free setting.

Aims and Objectives: To determine and analyze the dimensions of lumbar vertebral pedicles in adult Indian population.

Methods: This is a prospective and observational study conducted on 35 specimens of lumbar vertebrae. The study considered 35 dry, fully ossified, healthy lumbar vertebral pairs from the Department of Anatomy were used in the investigation. All vertebrae were divided into typical (L1 to L4) and atypical categories for the study (L5). The specimens were determined for variation in their dimensions and required analysis were carried out for proper analysis.

Results: Pedicles in normal vertebrae (L1 to L4) ranged in length and height from 8.86 millimetres to 10 millimetres and 13.12 millimetres to 13.89 millimetres, respectively. The typical vertebra's pedicle thickness ranged from 7.12 to 11.23 millimetres. PDL, PDH, and PDTh for L5 had mean values of 8.81 mm, 12.78 mm, and 16.11 mm, respectively. Pedicle axial length increased from L1 to L3 and then decreased from L4 to L5, with the mean transverse angle of the right and left side of the pedicle at L5 being larger than L4 (16.97 degrees and 15.82 degrees). The study found that there is shows statistically significant variations in the sizes of the pedicles of each of the five lumbar vertebrae. With the exception of height, a highly significant ($P < 0.01$) difference was seen for all measures.

Conclusion: The study has concluded that there are significant differences in dimension of pedicles of both the typical and atypical variant of lumbar vertebrae.

Keywords: Vertebrae, Pedicles, Lumbar Vertebrae, Bony Structure.

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Introduction

During lumbar spinal stabilization procedures, the pedicles of the lumbar spine, which are larger and stronger and frequently employed for screw fixation, are utilized [1]. Many lumbar column disorders, such as fractures, degenerative changes, cancer, or lumbar instabilities, call for "spinal fixation." Low back pain and other lumbar spinal disease-related symptoms are more common in the current world [2].

When conducting instrumented spinal fusion, having a thorough knowledge of bone structure is crucial. Devastating consequences can ensue from a slight change in screw trajectory [3,12]. An operating surgeon can carry out these treatments more accurately and safely if they are aware of slight anatomical heterogeneity. Prior to implant implantation, general orthopedic surgery guidelines encourage templating with precise measurements [4,5]. Prior to screw implantation, the exact diameter of the spinal pedicle is, however, rarely known. When choosing the size of the pedicle screw intraoperatively, an estimating technique is frequently used, which entails the review of perioperative fluoroscopic pictures and an approximation of the pedicle diameter by the surgeon (PD) [6,11].

Given that incorrect screw size selection could theoretically result in screw failure and need difficult and expensive revision surgery, the clinical concern for inaccurate PD assessment, and hence pedicle screw size estimation, has great weight [7,8]. Recent research emphasizes how crucial it is to comprehend various pedicle isthmus shapes in order to perform transpedicular surgeries successfully. According to Li et al., endosteal width should be taken into account when choosing the pedicle screw size [9]. According to Banta et al., the maximum diameter that can be used for the insertion pedicle screw is the cancellous

dimension of the pedicle, which has been proposed as the effective PD [4]. They showed that there was a significant discrepancy between both the historically recorded diameter of the outer cortical and the effective cancellous diameter, suggesting that a safe screw selection might not always be possible with the use of traditional methods [10].

One of the minimally invasive treatments for lumbar problems is lumbar fusion. Due to its reduced invasiveness and quick postoperative recovery, it is commonly chosen over other surgical options. One method for ensuring proper lumbar stabilization when treating numerous vertebral disorders in the lumbar region, such as trauma, tumors, fractures, degeneration, and lumbar instability, is "transpedicular spine fixation." Appropriate morphometric information on the lumbar pedicles is essential to undertake these treatments in a risk-free setting [13-15].

Materials and methods

Study design

This is a prospective and observational study conducted on 35 specimens of lumbar vertebrae. These specimens were obtained from the anatomy department of this Medical College. The study was conducted from January, 2022 to December, 2022. The study considered 35 dry, fully ossified, healthy lumbar vertebral pairs from the Department of Anatomy were used in the investigation. All vertebrae were divided into typical (L1 to L4) and atypical categories for the study (L5). A "Digital Vernier Caliper" with a precision of 0.01 mm and a "Geometrica Protractor" with markings up to 180 degrees were used to measure the dimensions, which included height, length, axial length, thickness, sagittal and transverse angles.

Figure 1: Lumbar Vertebrae and Digital Vernier Caliper

Pedicle length (PDL): A measurement between two sites, one at the intersection of the vertebral body and pedicle and the other at the intersection of the pedicle and the superior articular process, is known as the pedicle length (PDL).

Pedicle Height (PDH): This is the tallest measurement possible at the back of the pedicle.

Pedicle Thickness (PDTh): Refers to the pedicle's maximal transverse measures at

its posterior end. **Pedicle Axis Length (PDAL):** the distance along the pedicle's long axis from the posterior end of the pedicle, where it meets the superior articular process, to the anterior face of the cortex of the vertebral body.

Pedicle Transverse Angle (PDTAn): is the angle created between the pedicle's long axis and the mid-sagittal line.

Pedicle Sagittal Angle (PDSAn): is the angle created by the pedicle's long axis and the body's superior surface.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The study considered specimens from the anatomy department of this hospital. The included specimens were ensured that had no sign of fracture or specimens were otherwise broken during dissection or storage. Those specimens were excluded which were not visible clearly or damaged in any form.

Statistical analysis

The study used SPSS Version 25 for effective analysis. Each side's mean and Standard Deviations (SD) were computed. The "ANOVA" test was used to calculate the statistical differences. Millimetres and degrees were used to measure the pedicle parameters.

Results

Pedicles in normal vertebrae (L1 to L4) ranged in length and height from 8.86 millimetres to 10 millimetres and 13.12 millimetres to 13.89 millimetres, respectively. The typical vertebra's pedicle thickness ranged from 7.12 to 11.23 millimetres. PDL, PDH, and PDTh for L5 had mean values of 8.81 mm, 12.78 mm, and 16.11 mm, respectively (Table 1). PDL was seen to grow up until L3, but then diminish at L5. The PDH increased gradually from L1 to L4, too. But in L5, it was diminished. The thickness of the pedicle in the fifth lumbar vertebra abruptly increased in comparison to the fourth,

despite the fact that PDTh was raised from L1 to L5.

Table 1: pedicle lumbar vertebrae dimensions (n=35)

Vertebra		PDL(mm)		PDH(mm)		PDTh(mm)	
		R	L	R	L	R	L
L1	Mean	9.68	9.5412	13.5981	13.2405	7.1212	7.1509
	SD	1.2123	1.7512	1.8012	1.6121	1.3843	1.5134
L2	Mean	10.0058	9.6312	13.6443	13.4213	7.4732	7.4312
	SD	1.221	1.321	1.2891	1.1409	1.4689	1.3612
L3	Mean	9.8123	9.6234	13.8980	13.6123	8.7512	9.1289
	SD	1.3412	1.2411	1.3892	1.3721	1.3314	1.2745
L4	Mean	9.0009	8.8622	13.1602	13.1239	10.7598	11.2312
	SD	1.1843	1.1001	1.9412	2.7021	2.1532	2.1621
L5	Mean	8.8143	8.8601	12.7810	12.7601	16.1178	16.2234
	SD	1.4987	1.3700	1.9123	1.9541	3.4215	3.5775

PDL – Pedicle Length, PDH – Pedicle Height, PDTh – Pedicle Thickness, S.D – Standard Deviation

The measurements of the axial length and pedicle angles of normal and abnormal lumbar vertebral pedicles are shown in Table 2. From L1 through L4, the transverse angle of the pedicle grew slowly, but at L5, it increased more suddenly than at L4. Pedicle axial length increased from L1 to L3 and then decreased from L4 to L5, with the mean transverse angle of the right

and left side of the pedicle at L5 being larger than L4 (16.97 degrees and 15.82 degrees). However, it was shown that L5's mean sagittal angle and mean axis length of the pedicle were lower than those of L4. However, neither the sagittal angle of the typical nor the atypical vertebrae much changed.

Table 2: Sagittal, transverse, axial length, and angles of lumbar vertebrae (n=35)

Vertebra		PDTAn(Degree)		PDSn(Degree)		PDAL(mm)	
		R	L	R	L	R	L
L1	Mean	11.7537	11.6431	6.2897	6.2891	35.2413	35.2923
	SD	0.9514	0.8503	0.5132	0.5435	2.0797	2.1134
L2	Mean	13.2846	13.2698	7.1899	7.1891	36.354	36.2678
	SD	0.9689	0.9801	0.6904	0.6543	1.9905	2.2412
L3	Mean	14.5911	14.4534	8.245	8.245	37.5123	37.4315
	SD	1.0701	0.9312	0.8795	0.8989	2.4879	2.4962
L4	Mean	16.9789	15.8228	8.3523	8.4324	36.2865	35.9609
	SD	1.3432	2.9312	0.9912	0.8456	2.2756	2.0413
L5	Mean	22.6409	21.702	7.8879	7.7344	34.4345	34.3712
	SD	1.1301	3.5309	1.1798	1.2235	2.1897	2.3902

PDTAn – Pedicle Transverse Angle, PDSAn – Pedicle Sagittal Angle, PDAL – Pedicle Axial Length, S.D – Standard Deviation

Table 3 shows statistically significant variations in the sizes of the pedicles of each of the five lumbar vertebrae. With the exception of height, a highly significant ($P < 0.01$) difference was seen for all

measures. Additionally, there was a statistically significant association ($p < 0.05$) between the vertebrae. dimensions of the lumbar pedicles on the left and right sides of the atypical and typical lumbar

Table 3: Significant variations in the size of pedicles

	F-value	p-value	Significance
Length	7.25	0.01	HS
Height	2.59	0.047	S
Thickness	147.12	0.021	HS
Transverse Angle	709.12	0.012	HS
Sagittal Angle	42.11	0.0352	HS
Axial Length	14.39	0.018	HS

HS: Highly Significant (p -value < 0.01); S: Significant (p -value < 0.05); NS: Not Significant (p -value > 0.05)

Discussion

Within each race, there are variations in the size and shape of the pedicles of the human spine. The dimensions and angle of the spine pedicles in Koreans from T1 to L5 were examined by the authors. Transverse diameter, super inferior diameter, anteroposterior pedicle angle, horizontal pedicle angle, and pedicle axis angle were all measured. In order to fix transpedicular screws and explain the differences between other races and Koreans, the study collected indices of pedicle morphology in Koreans [16]. In order to fix transpedicular screws and explain the differences between other races and Koreans, the study collected indices of pedicle morphology in Koreans. At the L5 level, the pedicle's transverse dimension was at its broadest, while at the T4 level, it was at its thinnest. At the T12 level, the pedicle's super inferior dimension was at its broadest; at the T1 level, it was at its narrowest. The pedicles of T11 and T12 were angled lateral in the transverse plane. At the T4 level, the anterior-posterior angle grew quickly, with the T1 level having the largest angle. The lumbar vertebra's horizontal angle in the sagittal plane was nearly parallel to the horizontal plane. At the L3 level, the pedicle axis was the

longest; at the T1 level, it was the shortest. Males had a bigger transverse dimension of the pedicle than females did in every location [20,17].

Using simple anteroposterior radiographic images of the lumbar spines of female and male participants between the ages of 10 and 65 years, the vertical and horizontal diameters of the pedicles of the lumbar vertebrae were evaluated. The findings of a recent study revealed that the male and female pedicle diameters differed significantly from one another. Although there was an overall increase in both horizontal and vertical diameters when the age groups were tracked from the youngest to the oldest, the changes were characterized by increases in diameters in certain age groups and decreases in others. Both the vertical and horizontal diameters showed different patterns of age-related change [21,19].

To ascertain the variations between the sexes and the precision of radiographic measurement, the pedicles of the lumbar vertebrae were examined both radiographically and directly. While the transverse and sagittal angles of the pedicle did not significantly differ between the

sexes, comparisons demonstrated that the average sagittal and transverse diameters of the pedicles as well as the distance from the anterior aspect of the cortex of the vertebral body to the posterior aspect of the laminar cortex along the center line of the pedicles were 5.3 to 20.2% greater in men. Even without magnification, measurements were found to be more accurate on radiographs and computerized tomographic scans than direct measurements. The sagittal and transverse dimensions of the pedicle of the 5th lumbar vertebra, nevertheless, were directly measured and were larger than the radiography measures [22,18].

Recently, a study was carried out to gather information on pedicle width and height in various locations and to look into the variance and difference between them. The biggest pedicle height and width were found in Oceania, then in America. East and Southeast Asia were the two Asian regions with the biggest pedicle widths, whereas South Asian and Chinese pedicle widths were comparable [25]. The pedicle height of East and Southeast Asian, Chinese, and West Asian in the Asian range is similar, in contrast to the variation pattern of pedicle width, while the pedicle height of South Asian is statistically substantially smaller than the first three. The study finds that despite belonging to distinct ethnic groups, people in various places have comparable patterns of variance in pedicle width and height. [26] Geographically proximate populations are more likely to experience this phenomenon, which may be connected to interethnic integration as a result of population movement between nearby places. Geographic location and the morphological traits of the human lumbar pedicle are related [23,24].

Conclusion

The study has concluded that there are significant differences in dimension of pedicles of both the typical and atypical variant of lumbar vertebrae. The study has shown that each dimension factor like length, thickness, height, sagittal angle,

transverse angle, axial length, are all significantly varied. The range of variation is considerable and the proper evidence is brought by our study which will contributing knowledge for the surgeons for their successful and effective operation. This study is centre specific study and so, there is a need to conduct more studies with varied population in the future.

However, this study has highlighted important points which will be helpful for the academicians as well as the surgeons.

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